

Percent diseased leaf area (%DLA) for both B1 and BB was measured three times at 5-d intervals, beginning with initiation of lesions. The table shows final DLA due to B1 and BB. Most entries appear

susceptible to B1 and BB. IRRI Acc. No. 102468-2, 102468-3 (*O. rufipogon/O. nivara*) and 103837-1, 103837-2, and 103840-1 (*O. nivara*) showed resistance to B1; No. 102465 (*O. nivara*) and

102467 and 103406 (*O. rufipogon/O. nivara*) showed resistance to BB.

These wild rices may be used in wide hybridization to transfer resistance genes to cultivated rices. ■

Pest resistance – insects

Evaluation of brown planthopper (BPH)- and whitebacked planthopper (WBPH)-resistant hybrid rices for resistance to Angoumois grain moth (AGM)

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AGM *Sitotroga cerealella* Olivier is a major pest of stored rice in China. We evaluated 15 rice hybrids with resistance to BPH or WBPH (Table 1) for their resistance to AGM.

AGM were reared on wheat seeds in the laboratory. Moisture content of rice grain was adjusted to 13%, and 5 g of tested hybrid seed were infested with 100 eggs of AGM. Treatments were in a split-plot design with four replications. After infestation, the samples were stored at 27°C and 75% relative humidity.

Resistance was evaluated on several parameters, including percentage emerging adults, grain weight loss, development period, and susceptibility index (SI). SI was based on the formula

$$SI = \frac{\text{natural log number of emerging adults}}{\text{average development period}} \times 100$$

Susceptibility was determined by this scale:

Damage scale	Emerging adults (%)
Resistant	<10
Moderately resistant	10-20
Susceptible	>20

Table 1. Resistance of hybrids of BPH and WBPH.

Hybrid	CMS/restorer	Reaction ^a	
		BPH	WBPH
Shan You 6	Zhen Shen 97 A/IR24	1	6.3
Shan You 30	Zhen Shen 97 A/IR30	3	7.7
Shan You 54	Zhen Shen 97 A/IR54	1	7
Shan You 56	Zhen Shen 97 A/IR56	2.3	3
Shan You 63	Zhen Shen 97 A/Ming Hui 63	7.7	4.3
Shan You 64	Zhen Shen 97 A/Ce 64 ^b	1.7	2.3
Shan You 177	Zhen Shen 97 A/IR26/Zhai Ye Qing 8	1	1.7
Shan You 6161-8	Zhen Shen 97 A/Gui 8	1.7	3.7
Shan You Zhu Hui Zao	Zhen Shen 97 A/Zhu Hui Zao	1	6.3
Wei You 6	V20 A/IR26	1	3
Wei You 35	V20 A/26 Zhai Zao	1	1.7
Wei You 64	V20A/Ce64 ^c	1	1.7
Wei You 98	V20 A/98	6.3	1.7
Xin You 6	Xin Qing Ai A/IR26	3	4.6
Liu You 30	6064 A/IR30	1.7	9

^aScore 1-9 : 1 = highly resistant, 9 = highly susceptible. ^b IR9761-19-1-64. ^c IR2061/IR661.

Table 2. Resistance of hybrids to AGM.

Hybrid	Emerging adults (%)	Development period (d)	Susceptibility index	Grain weight loss (%)	Damage scale ^a
Shan You 6	18.8	35.2	8.18	3.2	MR
Shan You 30	37.5	27.0	13.45	13.5	S
Shan You 54	23.3	33.3	9.41	8.2	S
Shan You 56	11.0	28.6	8.40	3.4	MR
Shan You 63	25.5	38.4	8.35	9.4	S
Shan You 64	40.5	28.2	13.19	13.6	S
Shan You 177	24.5	33.7	9.48	7.4	S
Shan You 6161-8	25.3	37.9	8.53	9.1	S
Shan You Zhu Hui Zao	42.0	33.1	11.25	11.3	S
Wei You 6	28.0	35.3	9.47	9.3	S
Wei You 35	20.5	34.7	8.68	7.5	S-MR
Wei You 64	34.5	34.3	10.32	12.5	S
Wei You 98	40.5	33.2	10.95	13.3	S
Xin You 6	34.8	26.6	13.30	13.3	S
Liu You 30	39.8	31.7	11.63	13.0	S
Cauvery ^b (resistant check)	4.7	35.6	4.37	0.4	R
Xing Hui Zhan 1 (susceptible check)	43.5	27.4	13.73	8.9	S

^aR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible. ^b Pureline variety.

No resistant hybrids were found, and only Shan You 6 and Shan You 56 were rated moderately resistant to AGM (Table 2). Shan You 56 was also resistant to both BPH and WBPH, and Shan You 6 exhibited resistance

to BPH. The hybrids were more susceptible to the AGM than were pureline varieties. When 63 pureline varieties were screened for resistance, 36 exhibited resistance and 19 moderate resistance. ■